

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

WEBQUESTS AS A MEANS OF FORMING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The article discusses the ways of forming a foreign language communicative competence among primary school students using Webquest technology. In the introduction of the article, there is given an explanation of the relevance and importance of forming a foreign language communicative competence in accordance with the requirements of modern society and the latest changes in technology development. There is provided an explanation of Webquest technology itself and its role in modern foreign language education. Moreover, the article suggests the methods of implementing Webquests in foreign language classes for primary school students.

Keywords: foreign language communicative competence, Webquest, foreign language education, English in primary school, critical thinking skills, active learning methods.

The rapid technology development and its application in education around the world require innovative methods and approaches to teaching as well. In the era of digitalization and the active use of social networks, foreign language education does not stand aside and tries to correspond to the new trends of the current time. It is recognized that our children belong to Generation Z, i.e. they are raised in a digital environment and can manage any kind of gadget effortlessly. This modern generation dictates new rules for learning languages because they become bored very easily and the school system must meet their needs by integrating Internet resources, social networks, and other digital technologies in foreign language classes [1]. The study in Primary school is the period when children's worldview, mental health, and social status are being formed under the influence of the learning environment, educational activities, and relationship with the teacher. Therefore, a foreign language teacher should organize the educational process with maximum benefit for the mental and intellectual development of students, since learning a new language can cause stress and anxiety among young learners.

Contemporary foreign language education includes not only the use of digital technologies but also the introduction of new methods and approaches to teaching. Language skills are currently considered in the context of intercultural communicative competence, for the formation of which the methodology of foreign language education is being continuously modernized [2, p. 222].

One of the first who mentioned communicative competence was N.M. Chomsky explained the difference between "competence" and "performance" in his work (1965) [3, p. 259]. However, most of the research in applied linguistics cites the work of Dell Hymes (1972) as a foundation for introducing the concept of communicative competence. In contrast to Chomsky's definition, he states that it is not enough to build gram-

matically correct sentences, because the goal of competence is to show systematically possible, feasible, and suitable ways to produce and interpret actual cultural behaviors [4]. Later, in 1980, applied linguists M. Kanal and M. Swain published an article in which they argued that communicative competence includes four components or so-called sub-competencies: grammatical, sociolinguistic, discursive, and strategic. This is the classification of components on which many scholars still base their research. [5].

The formation of communicative competence is one of the main tasks of foreign language education in different countries, in accordance with European educational standards. Since primary school students are children aged 6-10 years, the most efficient and acceptable way of teaching them is by using different games and active learning methods. Therefore, it is suggested to use Webquests in foreign language classes in order to form communicative competence among young learners.

Webquests were first introduced by Bernie Dodge, a professor at San Diego State University, and identified as an inquiry-based activity in which almost all the resources are taken from the Internet [6]. A Webquest allows teachers to make the lesson more absorbing and engaging because of using interactive methods and technologies. While using Webquests, students have access to many authentic, appropriate, and up-to-date materials that can regulate their meta-cognitive thinking skills and form the relevant background for upcoming social interactions. This technology has a clear structure that should be followed in the design process however teachers need to create them according to the interests and learning styles of their students.

The first stage of a Webquest is an introduction, in which foreign language teachers can present the main topic of the lesson and key vocabulary that can be used during the next steps.

In the task section, teachers should introduce the central question and explain to learners what kind of

assignments they will complete in the next stage. Tasks in Webquests must be connected with real-life situations and increase their involvement.

The process stage of a Webquest includes familiarization with the materials taken from the Internet and fulfillment of all the given tasks. In the case of a language class, it is acceptable to activate the introduced vocabulary, integrate the new grammar structure, or consolidate the learned one. Students can be given one enormous or several small projects to present at the end of a process stage.

The final section is devoted to evaluating students' presentations and making conclusions about the learning outcome. Students can be evaluated not only by teachers but also by their peer students.

For the successful implementation of this technology for English classes in primary schools, it is necessary to select pedagogical approaches and methods that coincide with the strategies of Webquest, which support the principles of constructivism.

According to constructivist theory, people tend to create new concepts and connections through previous experiences and combine new information with what they already know. The origin of this theory is closely associated with the theory of cognitive development of the Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget [7, p. 206]. The main idea of constructivism is that active learning allows students to accumulate their own knowledge and understand their point of view. Since this approach highly values creative and active participation in the classroom, it can be perfectly intertwined with Webquest technology.

As stated in the works of Tom March, Webquests are inquiry-oriented activities that consider using sources of information taken directly from the Internet. Inquiry-based learning allows students to come to an understanding of a concept on their own and identify their social and cognitive needs [8]. Instead of being passive participants, they are actively engaged in discovering new topics and expanding their cognitive abilities. When students learn the material through hands-on activities, they establish a connection between the classroom and the real world, which contributes to the development of higher-level thinking and communication skills.

The next principle of constructivist theory related to Webquest technology is the application of the student-centered approach. This approach focuses on the needs, abilities, and interests of the students, and the teacher, in turn, acts as a facilitator. Instead of beginning the lesson with an explanation of grammar rules, the teacher helps students learn them on their own, as in a flipped classroom. A student-centered approach also includes project-based learning, in which students work in groups, conduct research, find solutions to the given problem, and, as a result, present the final product.

Webquests can also be designed for content-based learning. In foreign language education, this approach focuses on the subject and content of the lesson rather than learning the grammar. Moreover, students can be able to study what truly fascinates them, ranging from

a serious scientific topic to a story of their favorite celebrities. In order to master a certain subject or topic, students use the target language, which corresponds to the way how people initially learn their mother tongue [9].

Nevertheless, All the above-mentioned approaches cannot promise equal involvement and success for students in acquiring a foreign language. To solve this arduous task, teachers can use the method of scaffolding that gives support and the opportunity for students to keep pace with the school curriculum. scaffolding is necessary especially for primary school children because they need more time to process new ideas and sources of information. Therefore, this method along with the Webquest technology provides all the opportunities for young learners and their teachers to form and develop a foreign language communicative competence. They can access individualized instructions, authentic materials, and games that increase their engagement and develop higher-order thinking skills.

The Rector of Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages Kunanbayeva S.S. supports the idea of using a competency-based approach to form a particular competence. In her monograph, communicative competence is considered one of the components of intercultural communicative competence including linguoculturological, social, socio-culturological, conceptual, cognitive, and personality-centered. From her point of view, the result of competence formation corresponds to the highest goal of education such as preparing students for social adaptation, professional career path, self-development, and independent choice of a lifestyle [10, p. 110]. The competency-based approach similar to Webquest technology combines several aspects of learning and teaching that develop abilities and build experiences necessary for successful social and cultural interaction.

Taking into account age features and psychological development of primary school students, communicative competence can be divided into the following skills and abilities:

- Oral communication in standard cultural, educational, and everyday situations;
- Reading and understanding simple authentic texts;
- Basic storytelling about themselves and their surroundings, explaining opinions and expressing feelings;
- Receiving and transmitting information, retelling what was read or heard;
- Expressing thoughts in a written form;
- Basic grammar skills: punctuation, spelling, basic vocabulary;
- Awareness of social and cultural norms of communication: formality, politeness, and adequate response to the different cultural identities.

Forming all the aforementioned skills with the help of Webquest technology requires a thorough analysis and selection of relevant activities. Bernie Dodge offers the following types of tasks: retelling, mystery, journalistic, compilation, design, consensus building, analytical, persuasion, self-knowledge, judgement, scientific, and creative product tasks [11].

There is a clear advantage in implementing these Webquest tasks to form a foreign language communicative competence among primary school children because each of them can be used to develop different language aspects and critical thinking skills. For example, while a retelling task requires a set of skills such as reading/listening comprehension, paraphrasing, and grammar, in order to activate new vocabulary students can be given compilation tasks. One of the features of this task is that children collect all the given materials in the form of different collections (a cookbook, a virtual exhibition, a guide) according to the given topic. To form analytical and critical thinking skills it is suggested to use journalistic, analytical, and mystery tasks that require analyzing different kinds of information, making research on the given problem, and finding proper solutions. As mentioned before, primary school students need more active learning methods such as playing games, drawing pictures, or creating arts and crafts, therefore, teachers can give them Webquests with design, self-knowledge, and creative product tasks.

Conclusion

Considering all the facts, this article finds that Webquest technology is one of the efficient tools for forming foreign language communicative competence among primary school students. Integrating this method into foreign language classes allows teachers to engage young learners to actively participate in lessons and achieve high-quality results. Moreover, by using authentic materials and up-to-date information taken from the internet, students will be able to improve not only their listening, reading, writing, and speaking skills, but will also have the opportunity to immerse themselves in the culture and modern society of a foreign country. The result of the theoretical study revealed the need for developing a methodology for the formation of foreign language communicative competence among primary school students using Webquest technologies and the implementation of experimental work for more accurate outcomes.

COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH TO EDUCATION

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КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ОБРАЗОВАНИЮ

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Abstract

This article deals with the principles and foundations of a competent approach to education. The rules and regulations for the creation of this approach in education are considered. It also examines the detailed pros and cons of this type of education.